

INTEREST OF USING THE SNAP DUO ST PLUS KIT FOR THE DETECTION OF ANTIBIOTIC RESIDUES IN RAW COW'S MILK ON DAIRY FARMS IN NORTHEASTERN ALGERIA

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Özet

Bu çalışma, 12 süt çiftliğinde toplanan çiğ sütlerde antibiyotik kalıntısı olup olmadığını araştırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Çalışma, süt ineklerinde kullanılan antibiyotik moleküllerini tanımlamak için çalışma bölgesinde dağıtılan pratik veteriner hekimler arasında yürütülen bir ankete ve ardından bir metot enzim immunoassay ile toplanan sütte antibiyotik kalıntılarının araştırılmasına dayanmaktadır.

Anketlerin analizi mastitisin en yaygın hastalıklardan biri olduğunu göstermiştir.

süt ineklerinde karşılaşılan ve beta-laktamlar ve tetrasiklinlerin veteriner hekimler tarafından en çok kullanılan antibiyotik familyalarıdır. SNAP duo ST Plus Kit tarafından gerçekleştirilen sütte antibiyotik kalıntısı tespiti sonuçlarına göre, varlığı nedeniyle reddedilen süt miktarı, toplanan toplam miktarın %33,33'ünü temsil etmektedir. bir yanda sütün kalitesini iyileştirmeye yönelik düzenlemeler, diğer yanda da yetiştiriciler tarafından veteriner hekimler tarafından tavsiye edilen süreye uyulması için bu kalıntılarla ilişkili risklere yönelik yaygınlaştırma eylemleri.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Çiğ süt, Mastitis, Antibiyotik kalıntıları, Tarama, SNAP duo ST Plus kiti

Summary

This work aims to look for the presence of antibiotic residues in raw milk collected at 12 dairy farms. The study is based on a survey, carried out among practicing veterinarians distributed in the study region to describe the molecules of antibiotics used in dairy cows, followed by the search for antibiotic residues in the milk collected by a method enzyme immunoassay

Analysis of the questionnaires showed that mastitis is one of the most common diseases encountered in dairy cows and that beta-lactams and tetracyclines are the families of antibiotics most used by veterinarians. According to the results of detection of antibiotic residues in milk, carried out by a SNAP duo ST Plus Kit quantity of milk refused because of their presence represents 33.33% of the total quantity collected At the end of our study, it is therefore essential to implement, on the one hand, regulations to improve the quality of the milk, and on the other hand, popularization actions on the risks associated with these residues so that the time recommended by veterinarians is respected by breeders.

Keywords: Raw milk, Mastitis, Antibiotic residues, Screening, SNAP duo ST Plus kit

1. INTRODUCTION

Milk is a food of high nutritional value very rich in proteins, lipids, carbohydrates and trace elements. In Algeria, it is widely consumed, and occupies a prominent place in the food ration.(Belaid 2016),(Ramdane 2017)

In addition, milk can be implicated in several health problems, including chemical contamination, due to residues of veterinary antibiotics. And lead to the appearance of populations of antibiotic-resistant microbes which would lead to serious health problems. This is why it is imperative to seek their presence by different techniques.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Study site

The study took place for 6 months in the region of Constantine and Mila.

2.2. Investigation

With the aim of investigating the situation of antibiotic therapy in these regions, a survey based essentially on a questionnaire drawn up in a fairly broad manner allowing the collection of as much information as possible to study the different operating methods, structures and livestock management at the 12 targeted farms.

2.3. Methods

2.3.1 Analysis by the test

The presence of antibiotic residues was detected in different milk samples believed with the SNAP duo ST Plus kit.

Figure 1: The constituent of the SNAP duo ST Plus

2.3.2 Description of the SNAP duo ST Plus kit

The SNAP Duo ST Plus test is a rapid test in 6 minutes. This can be used on raw milk blends, whole, skimmed or partly skimmed as well as reconstituted milk powder. This test does not require the use of an incubator because the incubation is done at room temperature in the SNAP device.

The SNAP duo ST Plus test is an enzyme immunoassay using a specific conjugated receptor protein. This method makes it possible to detect residues of Beta lactam and tetracycline and cephalosporin in a mixture of raw cow's milk, at quantities less than or equal to the maximum residue limits

3. DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

The data obtained was subjected to a descriptive statistical analysis and allowed the presentation of results using Microsoft® software Excel

4. RESULTATS ET DISCUSSION

4.1 Recherche des résidus

Our results reveal the actual presence of antibiotic residues in milk cow raw material collected from farms during the study period. The absence of antibiotic residues is a quality criteria which determines the receipt or refusal of milk.

Table 1: Result of the snap duo st plus test

Farms	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Antibiotique	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-

Figure 2 : percentage of farms tested positive and negative

According to the results, the precedence of antibiotics is noted in four farms, 33.33% and their absence in the other eight farms, 66.66%; i.e. nearly a third, which represents a fairly high and worrying percentage for public health.

4.2 Frequency of diseases

In order to know the practices of use of antibiotics, we must identify by common diseases in the region and therefore know the treatments used. This allowed us to identify three dominant diseases.

Table 2: The main diseases encountered in the farms tested positive.

Diseases	Pourcentage(%)
Mastitis	50
musculoskeletal system	25
Digestive	25

In order to have recent data on the molecules of antibiotics most commonly used in dairy cattle farming, we conducted a survey of practicing veterinarians. They were chosen for their intervention in the treatment of diseases encountered in dairy cattle.

Figure 3: the main illnesses mentioned

According to the results obtained, mastitis is the most common disease frequently encountered with a rate of 50%, followed by diseases of the musculoskeletal system, digestive pathologies. The dominance of mastitis can have several causes poor maintenance with insufficient hygiene of cows, presence of pathogenic germs in environment, poor hygiene of milking machines or personal taking care of the cows. These very frequent pathologies have also been declared by other authors (Chatellet 2007),(Cazeau 2010).

4.3The state of hygiene on farms

Figure 4: The state of hygiene at the level of these farms.

At the level of three quarters of the farms, we note the presence of diseases and hygiene was poor, while in the remaining third the state was average.

The presence of mastitis with a very high percentage, followed by locomotor diseases can be explained by the poor state of hygiene of the premises.

Veterinary drugs are widely used in the livestock sector to control against diseases and improve animal performance (Mensah 2014). By Consequently, monitoring the presence possible drug residues veterinarians in milk and dairy products attracts a lot of public attention in the whole world (Agabriel1993). In Algeria, Decree No. 39 of July 2, 2017 sets the microbiological criteria applicable to food stuffs and requires the total absence of antibiotic residues in one milliliter of raw milk.

According to the work of Reybroeck *an all* (2004). he main causes presence of antibiotic residues in the milk are the accidental milkings of cows treated unidentified and the non-compliance with waiting times in . Thus, the more the standards for the use of antibiotics and waiting times are respected, the less the milk contains residues antibiotics. This non-compliance with waiting times is due probably at the educational level of the stockbreeders who remains weak on the whole according to preliminary surveys (Mohamed 2005).

5.CONCLUSION

The milk produced by cattle farms in the wilaya of Constantine and Mila contains antibiotic residues. Even if the rate is low compared to several other study results carried out in other regions in Algeria. But the risk of these residues is always present.

To deal with this problem of the presence of antibiotic residues in milk and to guarantee their harmlessness and protect the consumer, measures and regulations must be taken by scientists, competent authorities, breeders and dairy industries for a systematic screening of residues at each harvest on farms, the simple and easy use of the duo kit is therefore an interesting prospect, also rigorous and permanent monitoring of good hygiene practices is important in livestock buildings.

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